

The Doc wanted to Operate on the Wrong Leg!

by Brian Paul Kaess

Hello Everyone,

It was about 2008-2009 in sunny, beautiful Durango, Mexico, and I was living there in that sleepy, cowboy town with my wife Mayte and son Paul, who are both dual U.S./Mexican citizens. I am a U.S. Disabled Veteran (10%), having sustained a right leg injury during my service with our nation's beloved Marines. That being said, I did a sort of surgery checkup with a V.A. sponsored doctor named Dr. Treviño (there appear to be two surgeons named Dr. Treviño in Durango City). This was free of charge, so I said to myself why not- see what the doc has to say.

He examined my legs, just doing a sort of routine looksie. He looked at both the right and left knees especially. In the end, he advised me to have surgery on my left knee, because he felt, after x-rays, that he had noticed a possible hairline fracture or weakness in the left knee juncture, and that without further surgery, it might suddenly rupture and cause major problems right then and there. I thought he was way off. Although I had had swelling in both knees during my service, it was obviously the right knee & right leg that was the more serious problem. The right knee/leg was the one that was boarded out for a 10% disability.

Ironically, I was still able to run a bit on both legs, but I transitioned to a walking exercise routine to keep down the stress. In any case, I thought the doctor was 'off his bonkers' for wanting to perform surgery on the left knee. So obviously, I turned the doc down for elective surgery and never scheduled anything. Years later, I was wondering if he wasn't one of Peter Rogan's men in disguise! Ha!

The doc said, if I didn't have surgery on the left knee, I could expect a major fracture in the left knee within just a couple of years that could be life-altering. Well, it's been over 15 years now since that day, and my knees are doing better than ever, especially since I use insulin for my diabetes. Like my brother Garret Kaess, a former Loyola medical student, once told me: 'If you can walk, maybe you don't need elective surgery on your lower extremities?'

I'll just have to stick with that old formula, 'an apple a day keeps the doctor away!'